

EFFECT OF PERSUASIVE ABILITY, TECHNICAL ABILITY AND WORK ETHICS OF FIELD EXTENSION STAFF (PPL) ON SATISFACTION OF BROILER CHICKEN BREEDERS AT PT. SIERAD PRODUCE

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ABSTRACT

In the global economic era requires business breakthrough efforts to proactively consolidate themselves in order to strengthen competitive advantage, which no longer relies on comparative advantage in the field of raw materials, but also competitive advantages that can be achieved if business people have organizational competence, which means that the businessman can improve his performance. One way to improve performance is through improving human resources. One of the business businesses of PT. Sierad Produce, Tbk is a partnership farming system, where the cutting edge of this business is the Field Extension Officer (PPL), this field employee whose duties and responsibilities are to provide technical direction in the field to the company's breeders about how to run broiler chicken management in accordance with the standards applied by the company to produce good and correct chicken performance. So that the staff of the field extension staff are satisfied with business partners.

Keywords: Persuasive Ability, Technical, Work Ethics, Partner Farmer Satisfaction

PROEM

PT. Sierad Produce, Tbk is a company engaged in poultry, especially chicken, one of its business units is Commercial Farm. In this unit, the business sector manages broiler farms with a partnership system. The partnership system is a broiler chicken business or broiler business which is quite a lot done by farmers in Indonesia. However, the increasing price of feed and the fluctuating price of broiler chicken markets have made farmers' fortunes not improve, especially for small capital farmers. Not to mention

the impact of the spread of the bird flu virus which increasingly complicates the situation.

One way to breed that is considered capable of overcoming this is a partnership pattern. According to PP NO. 44 of 1997 concerning the Partnership: that to further accelerate the realization of an independent and reliable national economy as a joint effort on the principle of family, more concrete efforts are needed to create a climate that can stimulate the implementation of solid business partnerships among all economic life actors based on mutual principles require, strengthen each other and mutually benefit; (a) that the realization of a solid business partnership, especially between Large Enterprises and Medium Enterprises with Small Businesses, will empower Small Businesses to grow and develop stronger and strengthen the structure of an increasingly balanced national economy based on economic democracy and increase independence and competitiveness national economy; (b) that in order to accelerate the realization of such partnerships, especially between Large Businesses and Medium Enterprises with Small Businesses, it is deemed necessary to stipulate provisions regarding the procedures for organizing, fostering and developing them.

In broiler livestock business there are three types of broiler breeders, namely: Partnership, independent and commercial farm. The latter is owned by the manufacturer (Industry). The implementing partners (core) are industries such as the Japfa Group, Charon Pokphand (CP), CJ Feed, Sierad Produce, Wonokoyo, Poultry Shop (PS), and private capital owners.

Independent farmers are those who buy sapronak from the manufacturer and sell their own crops, so that both profits and losses are borne by themselves. If the livestock business capital is small, when experiencing losses, it will be difficult to start a business again. While partnership farmers do not buy sapronak and do not market their own crops. They earn income on the basis of an agreement.

The partnership system in broiler chickens tends to minimize the risk of losses that will be borne by farmers. As a result of various factors that might cause the business to lose money. With this system, farmers did not get excessive profits when the selling price of chickens soared, as obtained by independent farmers. If you want to start a business in broiler cattle but are still afraid of risk, there is no harm in weighing partnership patterns.

By following the partnership pattern, fluctuations in the chicken market price will not have a significant impact on farmer income. This is because the partnership pattern implements a contract price system that has been agreed in advance. Another case is if farmers do independent cultivation, prices that are too low will cause losses that must be borne by farmers and often cause farmers to go out of business. The choice of core companies must really be considered strength in the face of price fluctuations. In general, companies that are engaged in integrated poultry are the safest choice. This means that companies do not have to spend money to buy land, pay wages and maintenance risks.

Collaboration between Broiler Chicken Farms is a Breeder or Prospective Company Partner with good intentions and submits a request to become a partner, with the following requirements: Cages and equipment, Operational costs, Labor, Guarantees to Inti. Companies (Core) are: Scheme / Contract, Sapronak Supply (Day One Chick, Feed, Drug Disinfectant Vitamin Vaccine), Harvest Guarantee. In this livestock business, maintenance of chickens is monitored Weight, Mortality, Feed Conversion Ratio, Stock Feed, Update data Recording, Index Performance (IP) and then will be calculated Profit or Loss of Farmers.

To reach the company's target, one of the field employees / PPL is sent. Field Extension Officers (PPL) are recruited by companies with a minimum education in animal husbandry graduating from Snakma, D3 Livestock, S1 Animal Husbandry and D3 Keswan. If there is a high school education background and other majors it is possible because it has sufficient experience regarding the management of Broiler chicken maintenance. The target set by the Company for field extension staff (PPL) is 300 Index Performance (IP) and a target population of 15,000 to 20,000 per week. In addition, the company also sets the number of visits in each month. Field workers, have a list of names of partner farmers, who will be visited at certain times.

Based on field data, the 2016 Field Extension Staff (PPL) shows that the average Index Performance (IP) and target population in 2016 in the West Java Region have not reached the standards set by the Company. The results of IP performance and target population are influenced by the level of human resource capacity, in this case the field extension staff (PPL). The following below presents data regarding PPL.

Table 1. PPL Performance Results

No	Name	Area	Performance		
			IP	Population	PPL
1	Ahmad Khamdani	Pri. Barat	279	52.512	15
2	Albert Halomoan	Sukabumi	286	25.864	4
3	Angga Swarga N	Pri. Barat	274	22.878	4
4	Bambang S	Pri. Utara	224	12.029	3
5	Bangun Febriyanto	Pri. Timur	249	10.029	3
6	Berly	Pri. Barat	252	8.680	3
7	Budiarto	Pri. Utara	226	13.999	2
8	Budiono	Banten	283	39.394	7
9	Dede Miftah	Sukabumi	277	36.999	5
10	Dhimas Satria sakti	Pri. Barat	280	21.344	5
11	Endang S	Sukabumi	293	61.800	4
12	Eri Lestianto	Bogor	321	22.000	5
13	Fatkur Rizal FN	Bogor	290	22.500	4
14	Fauzan Tri Y	Pri. Utara	255	30.499	7
15	Giran	Bogor	266	34.009	4
16	Handy Indrianto	Banten	277	28.177	3
17	Haryadi	Banten	254	48.298	4
18	Hendra Masduki	Banten	231	60.140	5
19	Ipki Rifki	Sukabumi	289	27.794	5
20	Irsyad	Banten	257	28.482	4
21	Iwan PL	Sukabumi	290	45.700	8
22	Iyus Ruslia	Pri. Utara	264	38.857	7
23	Jatmoko	Bogor	320	16.100	1
24	Nurkholil	Banten	277	62.237	6
25	Kusnanto	Bogor	284	28.424	4
26	Muchlison	Sukabumi	283	40.338	4
27	Muhamad Radla	Sukabumi	237	15.671	4
28	Nanang Sutrisno	Pri. Utara	252	47.930	6
29	Panji Setiawan	Pri. Barat	237	23.614	4
30	Parwoto	Banten	257	106.716	9
31	Rezandy	Pri. Barat	256	12.316	2
32	Rohendi	Pri. Timur	254	19.350	5
33	Satria Wira	Pri. Utara	297	9.560	1
34	Satrio, Spt	Bogor	273	27.032	4
35	Sugeng Utomo	Sukabumi	211	24.424	4
36	Trisono Dwi Toma	Sukabumi	274	28.467	3
37	Ugi Sugiyat	Pri. Utara	270	34.636	4
38	Usup Supendi	Bogor	312	117.938	3
39	Yana Periyana, Spt	Pri. Barat	293	21.516	4
40	Yosefat	Sukabumi	275	26.121	5
Total			269	1.354.370	184

Source: PPIC PT. Sierad Produce, Tbk Unit Commercial Farm, 2018

THEORETIC

Persuasive ability

According to Wahyudi (2018) ability is a way of thinking, communicating and acting. While persuasive in KBBI means persuasive. In other words, persuasive ability refers to an ability to build effective communication, which is oriented to clarity in carrying out tasks, solving problems and achieving goals. In the study of Priadana and Iwan (2013) showed work ability has a value influence on satisfaction. Based on this understanding and previous research, it can be stated that the ability to work an employee unknowingly has been considered and given an assessment. Generally leaders or appraisers will feel happy to employees or employees whose totality shows their ability to work. He does not see what the risks and rewards are, but he focuses on his professional attitude. This is what causes many leaders or organizations feel happy and proud to have employees. Not only that, the company also provides commensurate reciprocity. for example salary increases, additional incentives, promotions and so on.

Technical Ability

According to Wahyudi (2018) ability is a way of thinking, communicating and acting. While persuasive in KBBI means intelligence to make things. The above definition confirms that what is meant by technical ability is to refer to an ability to act (work). In the research of Yulianto (2018), it was suggested that competence had a significant effect on satisfaction. The interesting thing from previous understanding and research is that the ability to work for an employee is fundamental. Technical ability is the main requirement for every employee accepted to work. Therefore technical capabilities need to be continuously honed and improved as basic capital in influencing performance appraisal. The benefits of technical skills for field workers are enormous. Usually, with that capability, he will be considered, whether it is worthy to be an employee in the future.

Work ethic

According to Wahyudi (2018) work ethic is a work spirit that comes from a personality (traits). In this sense work ethic refers to the personality of an employee who is always optimistic, upbeat, enthusiastic and so forth. All of that, comes from within him who has become a character. In Sutrimo's research (2018), it was suggested that work ethic is the nature, in which work spirit is built because it is based on a character

who likes to work, a character who likes to help, character likes to see problems from a positive perspective and so on, this is what makes him different from work motivation. One interesting thing is that work ethic gives birth to work behavior without calculation and the focus is to do good. Explanation of theory and previous research opens the understanding that work ethic is a nature of pleasure in working, working without calculation, working on a positive and optimistic basis, working with a sincere heart and the goal is to do good. This condition is difficult for every employee to have, and if there is, the organization will not view it only from one side of the award, which is financial, but more than that the organization will give its Trust.

Satisfaction

According to Wahyudi (2018) satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure. Generally feeling happy for a reason. This means that the leader feels happy because his employees are performing and employees feel happy because their performance is valued. In Engko's research (2008) satisfaction is a feeling that causes the birth of positive thinking and acting well so that the performance is achieved optimally. Based on previous understanding and research, it can be stated, that satisfaction is an emotional area, whose influence is very large on how to think, how to say and how to act an employee, therefore not a little variety of achievements is achieved. In addition, satisfaction builds good relationships, between leaders and employees, between employees, and employees with the company.

METHOD

The research method used is quantitative, type of survey research, and uses correlational analysis and multiple regression. Data were obtained through questionnaires consisting of 4 variables namely persuasive ability (X1), technical ability (X2), Work Ethics (X3) and farmer satisfaction, then filled by farmers as respondents. This study aims to determine the extent of the relationship between persuasive ability, technical ability, work ethic to the satisfaction of plasma farmers. To disclose this, a questionnaire is needed. This questionnaire consists of statements that are expected to reveal data from the variables studied at PT. Sierad Produce, Tbk Commercial Farm Unit. Data collected, then tabulated and processed using SPSS for Windows software. The series of analyzes consisted of validity test, reliability test, correlation test, partial test, simultaneous test and contribution test.

RESULT

Table 2. Partial Test Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4.328	4.778		.906	.370
persuasive ability	.558	.121	.568	4.631	.000
technical ability	.121	.128	.107	.946	.350
work ethic	.290	.131	.244	2.219	.032

a. Dependent Variable: satisfied breeders
 Source: Research Data, 2018

Tabel 3. Uji Simultan (Uji F) ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	245.964	3	82,018	26.389	.000 ^b
Residual	136.702	44	3.107		
Total	382.667	47			

a. Dependent Variable: satisfied breeders
 b. Predictors: (Constant), persuasive ability, technical ability, work ethic
 Source: Research Data, 2018

Based on the results of above data processed, the research findings can be presented as follows:

1. The effect of persuasive abilities on farmer satisfaction

The results of statistical calculations show that persuasive ability has a positive and significant effect on farmer satisfaction, with a regression coefficient of 0.558, a tcount of 4.631 and a significance value of 0.000. This finding means that persuasive abilities have an important role in increasing farmers' satisfaction. This can happen, because persuasive competence in this case is the attitude of PPL employees who are familiar, warm in everyday life, routinely asking about many things about what partners do, routinely explain in detail about chicken livestock, guide patiently and get involved in livestock raising efforts from the beginning to the end, it was empirically proven to help the partners. The livestock partners feel the presence of PPL employees is teachers in raising livestock, who are always ready to be asked about livestock knowledge, which is always ready to be asked for help in maintaining and overcoming livestock problems. This condition makes

the livestock partners feel satisfied with the existence of PPL employees. Therefore it is important for the company PT. Sierad Produce, Tbk to select the recruitment of PPL employees and then continuously provide training to improve persuasive competencies.

2. The effect of technical abilities on farmer satisfaction

The results of statistical calculations show that technical ability does not have a significant effect on farmer satisfaction with a regression coefficient of 0.121, a tcount of 0.946 and a significance value of 0.350. This finding means that the technical abilities of PPL employees do not make the farmers' partners satisfied. This happens, because in general the partners already have expertise in raising livestock. Therefore the field capability of raising PPL employees has no effect on the satisfaction of farmers. This certainly gives input to the company PT. Sierad Produce, Tbk in providing training to PPL employees to focus on mentoring and consulting skills, not on the involvement of PPL employees in maintaining partner farms.

3. The effect of work ethic on farmer satisfaction

The results of statistical calculations show that work ethic has a positive and significant effect on farmer satisfaction with a regression coefficient of 0.290, a tcount of 2.219 and a significance value of 0.032. This finding has an interpretation, that the work ethic or work spirit of PPL employees is very meaningful towards increasing farmers' satisfaction. This happened, because PPL employees showed a friendly and patient attitude in providing counseling or mentoring, as well as providing information about opportunities to get greater benefits from raising chickens, making farmers feel happy and comfortable. Therefore, it is not surprising if such an attitude arises, causing farmers to feel satisfied with the performance of PPL employees. This is an input for the company PT. Sierad Produce, Tbk to provide training to PPL employees prior to duty, so that PPL employees will be sincere in carrying out their duties and strive to arouse the morale of the farmers.

4. The effect of persuasive abilities, technical abilities and work ethic on farmer satisfaction.

Based on the table above, the determination coefficient value is 0.643. This

shows, that the variable ability of persuasive ability, technical ability and work ethic together explain the effect on the variable of farmer satisfaction at PT Sierad Produce, Tbk Commercial Farm Unit is 64.3%. While the remaining 35.7% is the influence of other independent variables, which were not examined in this study.

In addition, the data above shows the value of Fcount (26,389) greater than the value of Ftable (2.82), and sig. α (0,000a) smaller than alpha 5% (0,05). This indicates that the results of the study reject H0 and accept Ha. Thus, simultaneously persuasive capabilities, technical capabilities and work ethics have a significant effect on farmer satisfaction at PT Sierad Produce, Tbk Commercial Farm Unit.

The findings above confirm that the existence of PPL employees has an important role in the satisfaction of farmers. His ability is needed as a source of knowledge in raising livestock, his work ethic is a reference for farmers to always be optimistic and enthusiastic in running a livestock business. So, it is expected that the existence of PPL employees can bring success to both the company and farmers.

Based on the analysis and discussion above, the research findings can be presented as follows:

1. Breeder partners are very happy with the persuasive competencies of PLL employees which include good communication and interaction. This, reflected in the attitude of attention, caring attitude and attitude to help PPL employees.
2. The technical competence of PPL employees Haven't affect on farmers satisfaction. This is happen because in technically, the farmer partners are good at raising livestock. However, what is needed by farmers is assistance in increasing productivity, distribution and marketing channels, resulting in greater profits.
3. The work ethic of PPL employees is a driving force for partners to be optimistic in cultivating livestock.

CONCLUTION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion above, conclusions can be made as follows:

1. Persuasive ability has a positive and significant effect on farmer satisfaction with

a regression coefficient of 0.558, a tcount of 4.631 and a significance value of 0.000.

2. Technical capabilities do not have a significant effect on farmer satisfaction with a regression coefficient of 0.121, a tcount of 0.946 and a significance value of 0.350.
3. Work ethic has a positive and significant effect on farmer satisfaction with a regression coefficient of 0.290, a tcount of 2.219 and a significance value of 0.032.
4. Persuasive abilities, technical abilities and work ethics together have a significant effect on farmer satisfaction by 64.3%. While the remaining 35.7% is the influence of independent variables not examined in this study.

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